

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

IAP ALS BLS Group

National Convener
Dr Lokesh Tiwari

National President IAP
Dr Neelam Mohan

Secretary General IAP
Dr Ruchira Gupta

Jt National Convener
Dr Girish Bhat

Zonal and Joint Coordinators 2025-26

Central Zone

Dr Suresh Kumar Panuganti
Dr Atul Jindal

East Zone

Dr Kaustabh Chaudhuri
Dr Nandini Sinharay

North Zone

Dr Shalu Gupta
Dr Anuradha Bansal

South Zone

Dr Nithya T
Dr Lenin MR

West Zone

Dr Sanjay Bafna
Dr Akash Bang

CPR saves life

IAP ALS-BLS GROUP ANNUAL REPORT 2025-26

TRAINING • SCIENCE • SERVICE

A YEAR OF STRENGTHENING RESUSCITATION CAPACITY ACROSS INDIA

IAP ALS BLS GROUP 2025-2026

The year 2025–26 marked a phase of consolidation, expansion, and maturation for the IAP ALS–BLS Group. With a sharp rise in certification courses for healthcare professionals and an unprecedented scale-up of CPR awareness activities for the public, the Group has transitioned into a **National Capacity-Building Movement**.

This growth has been driven by the dedication of instructors, coordinators, and volunteers across zones and states, supported by the central IAP and with increasing adoption of digital systems for course management, assessment, and reporting. Alongside numbers, the focus remained firmly on **quality, uniformity, and scientific rigour**.

- As we move forward, governance strengthening, nursing ALS expansion, school CPR initiatives, and the establishment of long-term scientific stewardship structures will guide the next phase of growth.

DR LOKESH TIWARI
NATIONAL CONVENER

IAP ALS BLS GROUP

THE LEGACY OF NATIONAL CONVENERS

- **DR. SUNIT SINGHI**
- **DR. P. NALINI**
- **DR. LALITHA JANAKIRAMAN**
- **DR. SWATI BHAVE**
- **DR. SANJIV LEWIN**
- **DR. DEEPAK UGRA**
- **DR. ANAND SHANDILYA**
- **DR. JANANI SANKAR**
- **DR. L N TANEJA**
- **DR. ARIF AHMED**
- **DR. JAISHREE MURLIDHARAN**
- **DR. VIJAYALAKSHMI KULGOD**
- **DR. A K SHARMA**
- **DR. NARENDRA NANIVADEKAR**
- **DR. A K RAWAT**
- **DR. LOKESH TIWARI (Current)**

IN MEMORIAM

DR A K RAWAT

The IAP ALS–BLS fraternity remembers **Prof. A. K. Rawat** (Past National Convener 2023-24) with deep respect and gratitude. A visionary educator and gentle mentor, he played a foundational role in shaping IAP's resuscitation training culture.

His commitment to academic integrity, discipline, and ethical leadership continues to inspire generations of instructors and learners. Though no longer with us, his values remain deeply embedded in the work we do.

- *A humble tribute to a teacher who continues to guide us.*

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CPR saves life

Central Zone	East Zone	North Zone	South Zone	West Zone
Dr Manas Ranjan Sahoo (Chhattisgarh)	Dr Nani Tango (Arunachal P)	Dr Seema Rai (Punjab)	Dr Pragathesh (Andaman Nicobar)	Dr Mahesh Patel (Gujarat, Daman Diu, Nagar Haveli)
Dr Rashmi Gupta (Madhya Pradesh)	Dr Sudip Dutta (Sikkim)	Dr Geetanjali Jindal (Chandigarh)	Dr Lalitha A V (Karnataka)	Dr Bal Mukund (Maharashtra, Goa)
Dr Mounika Reddy (Telangana)	Dr Zeeshan Ahmed (Jharkhand)	Dr Pradeep Debata (Delhi)	Dr Ramesh Pol (Karnataka)	
Dr Sonia Bhatt (Uttar Pradesh)	Dr Rakesh Kumar (Bihar)	Dr Vivek Goyal (Haryana)	Dr Anu Marie Peter (Kerala, Lakshadweep)	
Dr A S Kireeti (Andhra Pradesh)	Dr Snehamayee Nayak (Odisha) (Himachal Pradesh)	Dr M. Lakshmi (Tamil Nadu, Puducherry)	
Dr Om Shankar Chaurasiya (Uttar Pradesh)	Dr Nihar Ranjan Mishra (West Bengal)	Dr Showkat Hussain Tali (Jammu Kashmir & Ladakh)		
	Dr Om Prakash (Bihar)	Dr Neha Agarwal (Rajasthan)		
	Dr Bhabesh Doley (Assam)	Dr Man Singh Parihar (Uttarakhand)		
	Dr Palash Ranjan Gogoi (Meghalaya)			

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

DIFFERENT COURSES

TYPES OF COURSES

IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)

IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses

IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course

IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP

IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)

IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

ALL COURSES: ZONE WISE

Zone	No. of Courses Year 2024	Through Website Year 2025	Addition al to Website 2025	Total Courses 2025
Central	73	109	61	170
East	36	67	15	82
North	91	112	33	145
South	67	74	14	88
West	58	41	12	53
Total	325	403	135	538

10.34 Courses per week

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES DIFFERENT COURSE

COURSE

NO.

IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)	84
IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses	15
IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course	3
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP	149
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)	152
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)	135

Total

538

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

NEW INSTRUCTORS INDUCTED

Zone-wise Distribution of New IAP ALS-BLS Instructors (2025)

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

ALL COURSES: ZONE WISE

Zone-wise Distribution of Total Courses Conducted (2025)

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

ALS PROVIDER COURSES

Zone-wise Distribution of ALS Provider Courses

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

ALS NURSING COURSES

Zone-wise Distribution of ALS Primer / Nursing Courses

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

CPR PROVIDER COURSES

Zone-wise Distribution of CPR Provider Courses

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

CPR MASS AWARENESS COURSES

(WEBSITE REGISTERED)

Zone-wise Distribution of CPR Mass Awareness Programs (MAP)

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

CPR eSanjeevani

IAP Digital CPR Awareness Module

CPR saves life

Go through the video module and get your
CPR Aware Citizen Certificate

<https://forms.gle/Mf7Aru44sTCPZUQM9>

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

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Dr Akash Bang

CPR saves life

This is to certify that

Ramesh Kumar

has participated in the
CPR Awareness Drive
conducted by

IAP ALS BLS Group

6/28/2025 20:09:17

Congratulations on being a

CPR Aware Citizen!

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

CPR AWARE CITIZENS CERTIFICATION

CPR MAP In addition to those registered on the website

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES

CPR AWARE CITIZENS CERTIFICATION

State-wise Participation in Online CPR Aware Citizen Certification Program

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

IAP ALS BLS Group

National CPR Day: 21st July 2025

CPR Awareness Activities 1st July-27th July

CPR Saves Life... ❤️

IAP-CPR-MAP
Facilitator Portal

IAP ALS BLS Group 2025-26

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

IAP ALS BLS Group

Offers the **CPR Aware Citizen Certification** Module

Supporting the Nation-wide CPR Awareness Week, Organized by the

Ministry of Health and Family Welfare

13th to 17th October 2025 (and Beyond)

For Medical Colleges, Hospitals, Healthcare Workers,
NGOs, organizations and Citizens of India

IAP-CPR Aware Citizen
Certification Portal

CPR Saves Life...

IAP ALS BLS Group 2025-26

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES CENTRAL ZONE

COURSE

NO.

IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)	21
IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses	5
IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course	-
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP	33
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)	50
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)	61

Total

170

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES EAST ZONE

COURSE	NO.
IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)	8
IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses	3
IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course	2
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP	23
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)	31
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)	15
Total	82

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITIES NORTH ZONE

CPR and ALS Courses Conducted at Kargil Pathankot and Jammu

COURSE

NO.

IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)	17
IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses	1
IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course	1
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP	45
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)	48
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)	33

Total

145

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITY SOUTH ZONE

COURSE	NO.
IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)	26
IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses	3
IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course	-
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP	35
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)	10
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)	14
Total	88

IAP ALS BLS ACTIVITY

WEST ZONE

COURSE

NO.

IAP - Advanced Life Support (Pediatric)	12
IAP-Advanced Life Support (Pediatric) Primer Course For Nurses	3
IAP-Advanced Life Support Instructor course	-
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR for Adult, child infant) for HCP	13
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Website)	13
IAP- Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation Mass Awareness Programme (Additional to website)	12

Total

53

E SANJEEVANI: CUMULATIVE MONTH-WISE PARTICIPATION

Cumulative Month-wise Participation (All Years Combined)
eSanjeevani - IAP eBLS Foundation Course

Month	Total Participants
January	4,621
February	3,888
March	5,308
April	2,969
May	2,895
June	3,054
July	8,573
August	2,792
September	3,745
October	1,794
November	1,890
December	1,589
Total	43,118

TRAINING MANUALS

IAP Manual for Management of Medical Emergencies at School

Under Medical Emergency Management for School Children- Child Safety Action Plan 2019

MEMS-Child Safety Project

BLS FOR PROFESSIONALS
DOCTORS, NURSES, PARAMEDICS AND OTHER HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS

basic life support

Under IAP Action Plan 2013 Golden Jubilee Year of IAP
Dr. C.P. Bansal (President, IAP-2013)
Dr. Suresh Gupta (Hon. Sec. Gen., IAP-2013)

Editors
Dr. L.N. Taneja
Dr. Lokesh Tiwari

pediatricians and nurses have been trained in Advanced Life Support to improve the care of acutely ill children. There is nothing more gratifying to a pediatrician than seeing smiles again on these pristine faces. We fervently pray that this momentum grows from strength to strength.

M. Jayashree

Second Edition 2020

IAP ALS HANDBOOK FOR NURSES

#Bring Back Breaths & Beats!

FIRST EDITION 2022

IAP ALS HANDBOOK
Embracing change in challenging times

#Bring Back Breaths & Beats!

Chief Editor
M. JAYASHREE
Associate Editor
VIJAYALAKSHMI KULGOD
Associate Editor
A. K. SHARMA

IAP ADVANCED LIFE SUPPORT COURSES INSTRUCTOR MANUAL

A ready reference for use in IAP ALS courses 2019

Dr. L.N. Taneja (Chief Editor)
Dr. A.K. Sharma (Associate Editor)
Dr. Narendra Nanivadekar (Associate Editor)

EARN YOUR INSTRUCTOR BADGE

IAP ALS-BLS-CPR SOP 2026
How to Conduct an IAP ALS-BLS-CPR Course
(Registration to Closure)

- 1 — PLAN & APPROVE** (8–12 weeks before)
Decide course type (ALS / ALS Nurses / CPR), Finalise date & venue, Coordinate with State Coordinator, Obtain ZC / JZC concurrence
- 2 — REGISTER & LAUNCH** (8–10 weeks)
Register course on www.iapalsbbs.com, Submit course fee & keep UTR, Ensure course is visible, Announce course & open registrations
- 3 — FACULTY, MATERIAL & LOGISTICS** (4–6 weeks)
Course Director & faculty confirmed, Equipment & manikins, Books & course material received from IAP warehouse, Distribute books to participants and instructions to read, Faculty travel/stay arranged if needed
- 4 — COORDINATION SETUP** (2–3 weeks)
WhatsApp Group A: Coordination & governance, WhatsApp Group B: Participants, Instructions shared via correct group
- 5 — FINAL READINESS** (Last week)
Venue & station walkthrough, AV, power backup, food & housekeeping confirmed, Participants briefed again, Faculty arrivals reconfirmed
- 6 — COURSE DAY(S)**
Start on time; attendance strictly monitored, Maintain academic discipline & rotations, Capture academic photos/videos
- 7 — ONLINE TESTS**
Pre-test / Post-test conducted on schedule, Ensure exam integrity, Resolve technical issues promptly
- 8 — DOCUMENTATION**
Banner, faculty, station & group photos, non-commercial visibility
- 9 — COURSE CLOSURE**
Academic closure by Course Director, Administrative closure by Course Coordinator
- 10 — POST-COURSE REPORTING**
Share summary with SC & ZC / JZC, Complete uploads & maintain records

Plan early • Communicate clearly • Close completely

**A badge of
Commitment
Science and
Service**

IAP ALS-BLS-SOP-2026
How to Become an IAP ALS-BLS-CPR Instructor
A Stepwise Learning & Mentorship Pathway

Step 1: Enrol as a Participant

- Attend an IAP-CPR Provider course and earn your CPR Provider certificate
- Attend an IAP Advanced Life Support (ALS) Provider Course
- Fulfil eligibility criteria for successful completion:
 - Skill stations performance
 - Assessments (theory + simulation) performance

Step 2: Demonstrate Competence & Attitude to be identified as Instructor Potential (IP)

- Demonstrate clinical understanding, skill performance, professional behaviour and teamwork
- High-performing and motivated candidates may be identified as Instructor Potential (IP) by the Course Director
- Selection is based on **competence, communication, and commitment**, not just scores
- Typically 1-3 candidates out of 36 providers in each course fit in this role

Step 3: Instructor Course

- IPs undergo structured teaching evaluation, assessment of instructional skills, communication, and professionalism
- Conducted under national oversight
- On successful completion and approval candidate is certified as an IAP ALS / CPR Instructor under monitoring

Step 4: Faculty Observation & Mentored Teaching

- Instructors under monitoring are invited to observe teaching faculty and assist in skill stations under supervision (minimum 2 courses)
- Focus is on **learning how to teach**, not just what to teach

Step 5: Continued Engagement & Growth

- Certified instructors participate in courses as faculty and receive feedback and mentoring.
- They contribute to training, awareness, academic and research activities in different roles.
- Participate in at least 2 courses per year to maintain your instructor status

Key Principle
Instructors are not created in one course — they are developed through competence, mentoring, and commitment.

Activities across IAP Centres for CPR training & Awareness

More pics

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

IAP ALS BLS Group

CPR Awareness Activities for Schools -2026

Kids Save Lives - India

IAP-CPR-MAP
Facilitator Portal

IAP-CPR Aware Citizen
Certification Portal

MOVING FORWARD TO 2026

IAP ALS BLS Group 2025-26

Every IAP ALS-BLS Instructor is encouraged to conduct at least one **CPR Awareness activity** for schoolchildren under the **Kids Save Lives – India Initiative**

Go beyond as much as possible. ..

Today, three schools took this step, and we commit to reaching many more
Together, building a generation ready to save lives...

More pics

Indian Academy of Pediatrics

IAP ALS BLS Group

CPR Saves Life...

IAP-CPR Aware Citizen Certification Portal

Appeal to ALS & CPR Instructors and Providers
Take the lead

Conduct at least one CPR awareness session for your circle

Family | Students | Colleagues | Communities
With just your voice and hands
Let's create a Nation of Lifesavers

IAP-CPR-MAP Facilitator Portal

IAP ALS BLS Group 2025-26

More pics

THANKS IAP ALS BLS GROUP

